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Long-term HCV infection in culture.

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We studied long term replication dynamics in a Huh7 HCV culture system with RNA-sequencing.

Citations

1. Levy, G., Bomze, D., Heinz, S., Ramachandran, S.D., Noerenberg, A., Cohen, M., Shibolet, O., Sklan, E., Braspenning, J. and Nahmias, Y., 2015. Long-term culture and expansion of primary human hepatocytes. *Nature biotechnology*, 33(12), pp.1264-1271.

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